

Nationalism In Popular Music In Thailand

Yang Xiaoli, Li Jia

Article Info

Article History

Received:
November 06, 2021

Accepted:
June 07, 2022

Keywords :

Nationalism,,Popular
Music, Thailand

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.6619100

Abstract

It is evident that Western traditions have influenced people's behavior in the East. Historically, Western systems have been viewed as modern, and developing countries such as Thailand have had a strategy of adopting and adapting numerous Western methods in order to modernize the country. This is still going on today. It can be argued that through globalization, powerful countries, particularly those in the West, impose their cultures, whether original or transcultural, that are created in the West on the rest of the world; and refusing this global imposition appears to be an act of separating oneself from the rest of the world.

Introduction

Economic and technical advancement have had an impact on music creation and reception in Thailand. Since the country's first interaction with the West, modernization has had an impact on Thai music. It contributed to the modernisation of Thai classical music and, more importantly, the birth of Thai popular music in the twentieth century (Thai-sakon & luk-thung). The global proliferation of Western popular music around the end of the twentieth century changed the Bangkok music scene. The Thai popular music industry has localized global music forms, and the new form of Thai popular music resembles its model, global popular music.

Thailand's music business

Thailand's music business is still in its infancy. Since the early 1980s, when various record firms arose, notably the most prominent local major record label, Grammy Entertainment, it has grown into a significant business. From the past to the present, the growth of Thailand's music industry has been a consequence of modernizing, looking abroad, and bringing back expertise to use at home.

Nonetheless, Thailand has an inherited "high culture" of musical styles. By adhering to old ideas, it has been preserved and protected from being ruined by the new global culture. As a result, it has nearly shut itself off from the reach of the music industry, which has a tight relationship with the media and is the most powerful distributor of music in everyday life today. Because most people listen to recorded music, traditional ideas about Thai classical music place it in a terrible position: music with no listeners will die away. When global culture, which the populace values, is introduced into society, the national culture is jeopardized. Since the 1980s, when globalization accelerated, environmentalist efforts have been developed to oppose the 'invasion' and advocate for the nearly extinct native culture.

Internal legacy has grown increasingly important for people who oppose external influences as a result of efforts to stress its historic presence. As Wallis and Malm (1984) have pointed out, resistance to globalization supports other emergent types of musical culture that emerged in the middle of the twentieth century. Not just Thai classical music (Thai-derm) but also all sorts of so-called classical 'oldies' of Thai popular music (luk-krung) and Thai country popular music (luk-thung) are praised in this situation. The conservationist does not simply advocate for the nation's musical heritage, but is also likely to condemn today's fashionable popular music, both Western popular music (sakon) and Thai popular music (Thai-sakon), for imposing foreign culture and causing people to ignore the valuable national culture (which includes the 'oldies' of Thai popular and Thai country popular music).

Thailand was in economic upheaval in the mid-1990s, and tourism was viewed as critical to the country's economic recovery. The campaign 'Amazing Thailand' was then launched for the 1998-1999 school year. As a consequence of the effort, Thai cultures have been revitalized in order to showcase them to visitors while also increasing public knowledge and responsibility for their inherited traditions.

The economic crisis has delayed the expansion of Bangkok's music business and has had certain repercussions on the music scene. While other kinds of music have long embraced modernisation, Thai classical music, which is tied to ancient values and hence safeguarded from progress, is now under investigation, and a compromise has been reached. The soundtrack for the national campaign 'Amazing Thailand' is Thai neo-

classical music, not traditional Thai classical music. The modernisation of Thai classical music began more than a decade ago, but it has only lately become more mainstream.

The ancient must be updated, and the new must be in touch with its roots. The phenomenon of patriotism in music has become stronger since early 1998, during the economic crisis. Thai musical identity is not limited to Thai traditional music; 'oldies' popular music, which is loaded with the spirit of Thai history, is a reflection of Thai identity, yet current Thai country popular music, which still preserves its Thainess, albeit in a rural manner, has stormed Bangkok's media. Because Bangkok has a greater prestige than the rural, the phenomena of 'hits' in Thai country popular music indicate that this genre's standing has increased. In general, the marketing target of Thai country popular music is the countryside; its expansion and acceptance within the capital may result in the creation of a new urban target for musicians, and the musical scene in Bangkok may change as a taste for country popular music is no longer considered shameful.

Globalization in Music Industry

Globalization continues apace in the final decade of the twentieth century. Global social policies follow a similar pattern. Societies with several cultures coexisting, as well as the hybridization of local and foreign cultures, may be found all over the world, and democracy is on its way. In terms of music, global popular music is the most powerful music consumed globally; it also stimulates local music creation and continues to shape transnational musical forms. There will always be a battle between the reception of global culture and the building of national culture, with or without the economic crisis, but the crisis has shifted the balance of power more toward the patriotic side.

Globalization has two major effects on cultures: the expansion of global cultures and the strengthening of local cultures to combat outside "invasion." Education has been utilized to instill national pride. Through the study of the nation's history and customs, education has in some ways pushed emotions of nationalism on students, but education has also updated knowledge by adopting modernism.

Thai and Western music are taught alongside each other in the required music curriculum at the lower secondary school level, however Thai music is prioritized when it comes to class teaching. Thai classical music has become a national emblem, a renowned component of the country's character. Thai classical music has been preserved and perpetuated through the obligatory national school curriculum, particularly as an extra-curricular activity. The Thai music curriculum, however, is not limited to Thai classical music: Thai popular (Thai-sakon) and Thai folk music - the basis of Thai country popular (luk-thung) - are also recommended.

Because the stream of globalization of Western popular music was strong at the time, and music making in society had developed in accordance with the fashionable global musical culture, the musical type that had the dominant role in music lessons in 1997, according to music teachers' practice, was Thai popular music (Thai-sakon), not Thai classical music (Thai-derm). Furthermore, while Thai folk music in its original form is barely recognized today, its modernized counterpart, Thai country popular (luk-thung), is well known among students as 'phleng pheun meuang' or 'phleng pheun ban' (both words allude to folk music). It appears that contemporary Thai music is gaining popularity both within and outside of the classroom.

Popular Music in Thailand

Nonetheless, the popular songs in the classroom that are offered in textbooks and that music instructors approve of are mostly popular "oldies," but new popular music is frequently incorporated into the classroom. Classical music, as well as old and modern popular music, appear to coexist in the classroom at the time, indicating that the conflict between what students want and what teachers value has resulted in a compromise. Music is traditionally seen as an extracurricular activity. According to the Thai curriculum, the educational value of music in Thai society is negligible. Looking more closely, the educational value of music will exist when a person learns music for the sake of musical knowledge or to further his/her education and musical career. However, music in the educational curriculum does not serve that purpose. Music is a required but unimportant topic. Its primary importance in practice, other from giving essential musical knowledge, is for cultural conservation (particularly Thai classical music), as recommended by professors, and for psychological advantages (i.e. promoting relaxing, lowering aggressiveness, and so on), as largely suggested by students. As a result, while educational value of music is not a major concern, it may be related to other more prevalent values of music. In general, learning music, especially in the more serious form of supplementary instruction, represents a social ideology in the sense that it brings the status of a privileged education into a household. Because extra music instruction is costly, the cost of music tuition also defines the economic standing of music students, and there is no equality between different types of music. A Western classical music lesson is the most expensive and is only available to those who can afford it, whereas a Thai classical music instruction is far less expensive (the music instruments also cost much less). The commitment to Thai classical music as part of the national identity, on the other hand, brings pride in acquiring it. This pride and the monetary worth of music are always in conflict. Thai classical musicians make the least in their careers, but the pride of transmitting national

culture compensates; nonetheless, this is not always considered as a fair bargain when contrasted to popular artists who are more successful economically and are liked by the general public.

In recent decades, a large number of part-time non-formal music schools have been formed, providing both classical and popular styles of Thai and Western music, and music courses in higher education are now more widely available. Nonetheless, classical music students' instruction is more structured and lasts longer than that of popular music students. A person must be taught properly to become a musician in classical music, but in popular music, the training is less formal, and popular music instruction tends to follow the current trend. Thai popular music (Thai-sakon) has a high economic value, as seen by its success in the music business and widespread appeal in the capital city. Popular music training courses, such as singing, have recently gained popularity as a result of singing competitions that have resulted in contracts with record labels for the victors. Aside from wanting or dreaming of a chance to work with a record label, advanced popular music students (much like classical music trainees, particularly in the Western classical music field) can also work as part-time teachers in music schools. The Bangkok music school industry progressed successfully until it was rocked by the economic turbulence that began in mid-1997. This has hampered the expansion of the music industry as well as additional music education, which is an essential aspect of music education in Thailand, as parents prefer to cut down on extra expenditure to cope with the financial circumstances.

As seen above, Thai people consider the educational value of music as being tied to national pride, relaxation provided by music, the ideology of musical practice, the apprenticeship system, and musical fashion, but in fact, the focus is on the first three concerns. For whatever reason, music is appreciated, music education is considered as useful, and it is gaining more supporters in society at large, both from the public and commercial sectors. Nonetheless, music is currently constrained to a place in the combined topic of 'Arts and Life,' which the majority of instructors reject, inside the national school curriculum (which began in 1990). The cutTiculum shortens the time available to instructors and makes it hard for them to progress efficiently. Many instructors report that they do not receive adequate support in the educational setting, and that their students' appreciation for music as a subject is low. The same problem persists, although it is more prevalent in public schools than in private institutions.

To take up the topic of music identity, conflicting emphases in education between nationalist issues and personal participation in everyday musical culture in society result in students having a fractured musical identity. Thai classical music, according to most students, expresses their national identity, whereas Thai popular music (Thai-sakon) expresses their personal identity. Furthermore, Thai country popular music (luk-thung) expresses national musical identity, despite the fact that most students are biased against its provincial style. They recognize that their preferred kind of Thai popular music (Thaisakon) is unlikely to become a national music emblem, yet this music connects them to the more desirable modern world culture.

The impact of globalization has shifted Thai people's perceptions of music as a job and a component of education. Musicians were once thought to be of inferior rank and to serve the ruling class. However, the phenomenon of worldwide popular music has demonstrated how much respect and economic prestige a musician may achieve, and this, of course, refers to popular music in particular. However, this provides an economic opportunity to amass riches and status above and above others who do not work in the business. More graduate and post-graduate music courses are now offered in education, demonstrating the acceptability of music in higher education. Music may be an inconsequential topic at school, but extra-curricular activities and tuition in schools or outside schools have aided in the advancement of music education to a higher level, since music is one of the most popular subjects for additional tuition. This is related to the identification of supplementary music tuition or music practice as a desirable pastime and a conventional upper-class activity.

The globalization of popular music has had a significant impact on Thai music movements, whether via the reception and celebration of global music, the adoption of its style by local music, or opposition to it through the strengthening of local traditional music. The more the imposition, the greater the adoption and resistance; both bring attention to music as a vocation and are beneficial rather than negative. Music careers are becoming more popular, and people's attitudes regarding them are shifting. The stigma of a career as unprivileged and insecure, as held by the older generation, is weaker among the younger generation. At the moment, there is a conflict between the elder generation's nostalgia for past greatness and the new generation's vision of a magnificent future.

Conclusions

The findings of this thesis verified Wallis and Malm's conclusions about the impact of globalization on local forms of music (1984). The thesis also highlights tensions that are tied to it. At the macro level, one element of the nation's desire to modernize collides with the reluctance of another portion of the nation's fear of losing its traditional identity. At the micro level of personal identification, a person desires to define himself/herself as belonging to the contemporary world by appreciating global culture, but yet belonging to a nation with its own individual identity. By encouraging compromise, globalization has weakened both the concentration of 'pure' indigenous culture and the intense celebration of global culture. Traditional culture, in

this instance Thai classical music, is not widely listened to in everyday life; yet, the fear of its slow extinction has led it to modernize in order to grab the attention of today's audiences. Simultaneously, in the aftermath of the economic crisis, people who create internationally influenced Thai popular music have come to feel responsibility for the survival of their traditional music culture, and have responded by incorporating parts of traditional music into contemporary music creating.

The position of musician, which has varied over time, is likewise a source of contention. Becoming a musician was traditionally a lowly service vocation, but in keeping with the worldwide trend, the music business has elevated artists, particularly vocalists, to the status of superstars, and being a musician has become a dream career with potentially large incomes. The stigma associated with the profession is dissipating. Nonetheless, when stability is considered, music is still supported as a pastime rather than a professional vocation.

Music education has grown in Thailand, particularly in extracurricular activities and supplementary tuition, which may lead to higher education, where progress is being made. However, obligatory music education in schools is heavily criticized by music instructors, not only for its content, but also because the shift in the new curriculum has devalued the subject in terms of time allocated for instruction and educational value. In the short term, music education in Thailand is expanding outside of the official school curriculum. Music as a business has just recently emerged in Thailand. The music industry has evolved in tandem with the global music industry. The music produced is virtually completely popular music: Thai popular (Thai-sakon) for urban audiences and Thai country popular (luk-thung) for rural audiences. Conservationists, in this case, teachers, frequently criticise the music business for not only failing to accept responsibility for preserving original Thai music, but also for attracting young people's attention to their primarily low-quality musical goods intended solely at profit. Because the industry is perceived to be committed to profit, the images of vocalists have been pushed to the front, and very talented musicians are thought to be less able to progress. This has kept young ears from hearing good music.

Responding to such assaults, record industry employees said that music creation is limited by customer taste rather than driven by business, and that because it is a business, it must avoid excessive risks. According to them, the music consumer does not prefer listening to Thai classical music, and the traditional ideas associated with Thai classical music have prohibited or severely limited its development. Thus, it may not be accurate to state that the music industry has ignored Thai classical music, because Thai classical music has refused to participate in the music industry.

The good news for musicians in general is that they are being recognized more than ever before. Their improved status, which is due in part to economic progress, benefits Western-style musicians (including Thai and Western popular musicians and Western classical musicians) more than Thai classical musicians, because income from performing and teaching is much lower for Thai classical musicians. Thai classical music is revered as a national emblem yet is underappreciated. It is not forgotten, but it receives insufficient attention. As stated before in 5.1.1, the reason for its static state as stated by record business employees is that it has failed to grow to meet the current moment.

The prestige of music careers in general has been harmed by the previous stigma, which led to their being seen as dishonourable, although evidence suggest that this stigma is receding.

For individuals working in the sector, music careers, which were once considered low-status, have now become part of a large industry of the 1990s. The stigma is currently felt more by elder artists than by younger ones. Middle-aged musicians have undoubtedly observed the shift. However, the career's long-term viability remains in doubt. Musicians within record labels have a higher standing than those outside; and within a record label, music-related occupations have evolved that are sometimes more solid and well-paid than a musical performer's career. In general, the music industry's expansion has created a bright future for music vocations.

These findings may indicate that, in the future, the Thai music scene's advancement in accordance with worldwide trends may decelerate as a result of the economic crisis. The blending of global and traditional musical cultures continues as a compromise that communicates both belonging to the globe and belonging to a specific area with a strong culture. This might be interpreted as a kind of defiance. Such resistance may be greater at times, and it will always occur unevenly in response to external factors that make the populace feel more or less responsible for preserving their national identity. According to music professors, it is necessary for the future of music education of all Thai students, especially those who cannot afford extra music instruction, that the national curriculum be revised again, and, equally essential, music appreciation and support for music study should be strengthened. These petitions are addressed directly to the government, whose policies and budgets have the potential to enhance Thai music education.

References

- About Thailand. (2002). Retrieved April 30, 2002, from <http://www.culture.co.th/English/thailand-in-brief.htm>
- Akenson, J. E. (1992). Social and geographic characteristics of country music. In K. J. Altamira, LeCompte, M. D., & Schensul, J. J. (1999b). *Design & conducting ethnographic research* (Vol. 1). London: Altamira.Amarin.

- Amarin. Aree, W. (1975). Andap pleng yod niyom sor sor sor [Fifty top hit of siang sam yod, radio station].
- Amatayakun, M. (1991). Tima khong pleng lukthung [The origins of Thai country music]. In Samnak-ngan-Kanakamakan-Watanatham-Haeng-Chat (Ed.), *Kueng satawat pleng lukthung thai pak song* [The mid-century of Thai country music, section two]. Bangkok:
- Amatayakun, M. (1991). Tima khong pleng lukthung [The origins of Thai country music]. In Samnak-ngan-Kanakamakan-Watanatham-Haeng-Chat (Ed.), *Kueng satawat pleng lukthung thai pak song* [The mid-century of Thai country music, section two]. Bangkok: Amarin.
- America's musical pulse: popular music in twentieth-century society* (pp. 83-
- Aree, W. (1975). *Andap pleng yod niyom sor sor sor* [Fifty top hit of siang sam yod, radio station]. Bangkok.
- Arnold, A. (1988). Popular film song in India: a case of mass-market musical eclecticism. *Popular Music*, 7(2), 177-188.
- Ashley, B. (1989). *The study of popular fiction*. London: Printer.
- Ashley, B. (1989). *The study of popular fiction*. London: Printer.
- Bake, A. (1999). Introduction: What's the story? Living though pop. New York: Routledge.
- Bake, A. (1999). *Introduction: What's the story? Living though pop*. New York:
- Baker, S. P. (2001). Rock on baby: Pre-teen girls and popular music. *Popular Music*, 15(3), 359-371.
- Baker, S. P. (2001). Rock on baby: Pre-teen girls and popular music. *Popular Music*, 15(3), 359-371.
- Bamrungrakorn, P. (2002). The immortality of Suntharaporn's songs. Unpublished Master degree, Chulalongkorn University, Bangkok.
- Bamrungrakorn, P. (2002). *The immortality of Suntharaporn's songs*. Unpublished Bangkok.
- Bangkok. Arnold, A. (1988). Popular film song in India: a case of mass-market musical eclecticism. *Popular Music*, 7(2), 177-188.
- Barker, C. (2002). *Cultural Studies: Theory and Practice*. London, Thousand Oaks and New Delhi: Sage Publications.
- Barker, C. (2002). *Cultural Studies: Theory and Practice*. London, Thousand Oaks and New Delhi: Sage Publications.
- Baskerville, D. (1995). *Music business handbook& career guide*. Thousand Oaks: Sage.
- Baskerville, D. (1995). *Music business handbook& career guide*. Thousand Oaks:
- BEC Tero, Sony take on Grammy. (2001, November 29). *The Bangkok Post*.
- Berger, A. A. (1998). *Media analysis techniques*. Thousand Oaks: Sage.
- Berland, J. (1990). Radio space and industrial time: music formats, local narratives and technological mediation. *Popular Music*, 9(2), 179-192.
- Bernett, A. (2000). *Popular music and youth culture: Music, identity and place*.
- Bindas (Ed.), *America's musical pulse : Popular music in twentieth-century society*. (Vol. 257-267). Westport: Praeger.
- Bindas (Ed.), *America's musical pulse: Popular music in twentieth-century society* (pp. 45-52.). Westport: Praeger.
- Bindas, K. J. (1992). Race, class, and ethnicity among swing musicians. In K. J. Bindas (Ed.), *America's musical pulse: Popular music in twentieth-century society* (pp. 83-90). Westport: Praeger. Books.
- Boonjan, N. (Ed.). (1988). *Cheud choo kroo pleng krangti neung: Saman kanjanapalin* [The contribution for the music meacher : Saman
- Boonmi, T. (2003). *Chatniyom lae lang chatniyom* [Nationalism and postnationalism]. Bangkok: Saithan.
- Boonmi, T. (2005, March 4). Sangkom lae watanatham lang kan lueaktang [Society and culture after the general election]. *Mathichon Sutsapda*, 25.
- Borgatta & M. L. Borgetta (Eds.), *Encyclopedia of sociology* (Vol. 2, pp. Boston: G.K. Hal.
- Brabazon, T. (1996). It started on the Queen street: New Zealand popular music, cultural identity and the question of landscape. *Continuum*, 10(1), 153-187.
- Brabazon, T. (1996). It started on the Queen street: New Zealand popular music, cultural identity and the question of landscape. *Continuum*, 10(1), 153-187.
- Brannigan, A. (1992). Post modern. In E. F. Borgatta & M. L. Borgetta (Eds.), *Encyclopedia of sociology* (Vol. 3, pp. 1522-1525). New York: Macmillan.
- Brannigan, A. (1992). Post modern. In E. F. Borgatta & M. L. Borgetta (Eds.),
- Bunyasingh, T. (1975). Pakkai chabab wannakam wiphath: O wannakam muanchon' [Oh yes, mass literature].
- Bunyasingh, T. (1975). Pakkai chabab wannakam wiphath: O wannakam muanchon' [Oh yes, mass literature]. California: Wadsworth.
- Carabo, A. (2003). *Lang mi style ad* [Behind microphone]. Bangkok: Mingmit.
- Castles, S., Kalantzis, M., Cope, B., & Morrissey, M. (1992). *Mistaken identity:*

- Chaipipat, P. (1991). Khokhit kiaw kap pleng lukthung [Some notion about Thai country music]. In Samnak-ngan-kanakamakan-watanatham-haeng-chat (Ed.), *Kueng satawat pleng lukthung thai pak song [The mid- century of Thai country music, section two]*. Bangkok: Amarin.
- Chambers, I. (1985). *Urban rhythms: pop music and popular culture*. Basingstoke:
- Chandler, D. *Marxist media theory*. Retrieved March 11, 2005, from <http://www.aber.ac.uk/media/Document/marxism/marxism10.html>
- Chandler, D. (2002). *Semiotics: The Basic*. London: Routledge.
- Charlton, K. (1990). *Rock music styles: A history*. Wm.: C. Brown. Chiangmai: Silkworm Books.
- Chunsuvimol, B. (2004). Family system and social relationship of Thai-Chinese ethnic groups in Boe Bae community, Bangkok. In R. Perera & P. Pradhan (Eds.), *Indigenous development for sustainable multi-habitations in Asian countries*. Bangkok: Urban Environmental Management Field of Study, Asian Institute of Technology, Center for Sustainable Development Studies, Tokyo University.
- Cohen, S. L. (1993). *Ethnography and popular music studies: Popular music*. Retrieved January 24, 2003, from <http://web2.infotrac.galegroup.com>
- Cooper, R., & Cooper, N. (1995). *Culture shock Thailand: A guide to customs and etiquette*. Singapore, Kuala Lumpur: Times.
- Cooper, V. W. (1992). Lyrical sexism in popular music: A qualitative examination. In K. J. Bindas (Ed.), *America's musical pulse : Popular music in twentiethcentury society*. (pp. 229- 236). Westport: Praeger.
- Country profile: Thailand*. (2004). Retrieved October 23, 2004, from http://www.news,bbc.co.uk/1/hi/world/asiapacific/country_profiles/1237845.stm
- Crane, D. (1993). *The production of culture: Media and the urban arts USA*: Sage.
- Crispin, S. W. (2001, August 2). Entertaining a very big idea. *Far Eastern Economic Review*.
- Dahl, L. (1992). Equal time: A historical overview of women in jazz. In *America's musical pulse: Popular music in twentieth-century society*. (pp. 205-212). Westport: Praeger.
- Dahl, L. (1992). Equal time: A historical overview of women in jazz. In *America's musical pulse: Popular music in twentieth-century society*. (pp. 205-212). Westport: Praeger.
- Damrongloet, J. (1990). Wannakam Pleng Lukthoong [Thai country music literatures]. Bangkok: Sathaban Thai Kadi Sueksa [Thai Studies Institute], Thammasart University.
- Damrongloet, J. (1990). Wannakam Pleng Lukthoong [Thai country music literatures]. Bangkok: Sathaban Thai Kadi Sueksa [Thai Studies Institute], Thammasart University.
- Damrongloet, J. (1990). *Wannakam Pleng Lukthoong [Thai country music literatures]*. Bangkok: Sathaban Thai Kadi Sueksa [Thai Studies Institute], Thammasart University.
- Eamsa-ard, L. (1995). *An analyzing of Thai popular songs in rock style*. Chulalongkorn University, Bangkok.
- Edensor, T. (2002). *National identity, popular culture and everyday life*. Oxford and
- Elite*. (2003). Retrieved July 26, 2005, from <http://www.dictionary.cambridge.org/define.asp?key=25209&dict=CALD>
- Elite*. Retrieved July 26, 2005, from <http://encyclopedia.laborlawtalk.com/Elite> *Encyclopedia of sociology* (Vol. 2, pp. 871-876). New York: Macmillan.
- Ethnicity*. Retrieved July 26, 2005, from <http://encyclopedia.laborlawtalk.com/ethnicity>
- Etzkorn, P. K. (1992). Music. In E. F. Borgatta & M. L. Borgetta (Eds.), *Encyclopediadia of sociology* (Vol. 3, pp. 1327-1332.).
- Farrell, G. (1988). Reflecting surfaces: Indian music in popular music and jazz. *Popular Music*, 7(2), 189-205.
- Fenster, M. (1990). Buck Owens, country music, and the struggle for discursive control. *Popular Music*, 9(3), 275-290.
- Flercher, M., & Shameen, A. (2004). *The sound of money: Thailand's Mr. Music has grand Asian plans*. Retrieved August 27, 2004, from www.groovybangkok.com/grammy-entertainment.htm
- Fornas, J. (1990). Moving rock: Youth and pop in late modernity. *Popular Music*,
- Frith, S. (1982). Music for pleasure. *Mass communication review yearbook*, 3, 493- 503.
- Frith, S. (1982). Music for pleasure. *Mass communication review yearbook*, 3, 493-
- Frith, S. *Popular Music 1950 -1980*. In *Making Music: The Guide to Writing, Performing & Recording*. New York: Quill.
- Frith, S. *Popular Music 1950 -1980*. In *Making Music: The Guide to Writing, Performing & Recording*. New York: Quill.
- Gatten, J. N. (1995). *Rock music scholarship: an interdisciplinary bibliography*. Westpor:
- Gatten, J. N. (1995). *Rock music scholarship: an interdisciplinary bibliography*.
- Geertz, C. (1973). *The interpretation of cultures: selected essays*. New York: Basic
- General information*. (2004). Retrieved June 5, 2004, from www.gmmgrammy.com

- Gilmore, S. (1992). Culture. In E. F. Borgatta & M. L. Borgetta (Eds.), *Encyclopedia of Sociology* (pp. 404-411). New York: Macmillan.
- GMM-Grammy. (2004). *Annual report 2003*. Retrieved September 2, 2004
- Greenwood. Geertz, C. (1973). *The interpretation of cultures: selected essays*. New York: Basic Books.
- Gubrium, J. F., & Jame Holstien, J. A. (1992). Qualitative methods. In E. F.
- Gunter, B. (2000). *Media research methods*. London: Sage.
- Hayes, M. (2004). Capitalism and cultural relative: the Thai pop industry, capitalism and Western cultural values. In A. Chun, N. Rossiter & B. Shoesmith (Eds.), *Refashioning pop music in Asia*. London and New York: RoutledgeCurzon.
- Hesmondhalgh, D. (1995). Global popular music, cultural imperialism and the English language. 22, 44-63.
- Hesse-Swain, C. (2001). *Speaking in Thai, dreaming in isan: Popular Thai television and emerging identities of Isan 'Lao' youth living in northeast Thailand*.
- Hirschman, C. (1992). Southeast Asia studies. In E. F. Borgatta & M. L. Borgetta (Eds.), *Encyclopedia of sociology*. (Vol. 4, pp. 2037-2041).
- Honak, N. (2003). *Toem kam ni tamnong*. Bangkok: Samsi. <http://www.grovemusic.com>
- Iawsriwong, N. (1999, October 19). Pleng puea chiwit khong kon chan klang [Song for life of the middle class]. *Matichon Sudsabda*, 19, 47.
- Iawsriwong, N. (2002). "Waduay Pet" Kwamkit tuaton lae akhati thang pet puying gay petsueksa lae kamaron [About gender: Idea, identity and sexual bias; woman, gay, sex education and sex]. Bangkok: Matichon.
- Identity*. (2004, November 8, 2004). Retrieved December 10, 2004, from Imagining the past, remembering the future, Cebu, the Philippines.
- In K. H. Chen (Ed.), *Trajectories: Inter-Asia cultural studies* (pp. 206-227).
- J. Bindas (Ed.), *America's musical pulse : Popular music in twentieth-century society* (Vol. 23-32.). Westport: Praeger.
- J. Bindas (Ed.), *America's musical pulse: Popular music in twentieth-century society* (pp. 45-52.). Westport: Praeger.
- J2K. (2002). *Kwa ja pen RS [The story of RS music company]*. Bangkok: Informedia.
- Jan-ngoan, A. (Ed.). (1993). *Concert luem mai long 40 pi Suthep Wonkmhaeng [Unforgettable concert for the fortieth anniversary of Suthep Wonkmhaeng]*.
- Jan-ngoan, A. (Ed.). (1995). *Concert cherdchoo krupleng krangti sam: Sa-nga Arampi [The concert for Sa-nga Arampi]*. Bangkok: Amarin.
- Jaret, C., & Boles, J. (1992). Sound of seduction: Sex and alcohol in country music lyrics. In K. J.
- Jaret, C., & Boles, J. (1992). Sound of seduction: Sex and alcohol in country music lyrics. In K. J. Bindas (Ed.), *America's musical pulse : Popular music in twentieth-century society*. (Vol. 257-267). Westport: Praeger.
- Jaroensuk, S. (1995). Dontri wijan [Critique of music]. Bangkok: Dr.Sax.
- Jiamthirasakun, S. (2001). Prawatsat ti pueng sang [The history that was just built]. Bangkok: Hok Tula Ramluek.
- Jiamthirasakun, S. (2001). *Prawatsat ti pueng sang [The history that was just built]*.
- Jones, S. (1992). *Rock formation*. California: Sage.
- Jopkrabuanwan, J. (1989). Pipitapan pleng lukthung [The museum of country music]. In Samnak-ngan-kanakamakan-watanatham-haeng-chat (Ed.), *Kueng satawat pleng lukthung thai [The mid-century of Thai country music]*.
- Jory, P. (2002, 2002). *Multiculturalism inThailand?* Retrieved November 30, 2004, from <http://www.hcs.harvard.edu/~hapr/winter/millennium/Thailand.html>
- Kaewsuk, P. (Ed.). (2002). *Nak taeng pleng thao pleng mai [Is songwriter equivalent to song?]*. Bangkok: Kokkok Kokit.
- Kamrai khong jing [The real profit]. (2003, June). *Pujatkan. Kanjanaphalin*. Bangkok: Choniyam.
- Kaplan, E. A. (1987). *Rocking Around the Clock*. London: Methuen & Co.
- Kent, S. A. (1992). Cults. In *Encyclopedia of sociology*, (Vol. 1, pp. 402-403).
- Ketudat, S. (1990). *The middle path for the future of Thailand: Technology in harmony with culture and environment*. Bangkok:: Thai Watana Panich.
- Kiatpaiboon, S. (1990). *The evolution of the music for life from a select audience to popular music for the general public*. Unpublished Master degree.
- Kidd, W. (2002). *Cultural and identity*. New York: Palgrave.
- Kita maha raja sadudi [The honour to King's music]*. (1987). Bangkok: Amarin.
- Klum-Silpa-Watanatham-Peua-Chiwit. (2001). *Senthang pleng peua chiwit [The path of song for life]*. Paper presented at the Ngan ramleuk 25 pi 14 tula" Komol Keemthong.

- Kong bap buranakan [*The complex corruption*]. Retrieved July 19, 2005, from <http://www.customs.go.th/Openfile.jsp?docId=K00016>
- Kosiyabong, B. (2002). *Bakery love is forever*. Bangkok: BMG Entertainment.
- Kotchayut, L. (2004, August 29). *Wijan wairun-pleng string [The criticism of teenagers and Thai pop rock music]*. *Matichon*.
- Kowapitakthet, N. (1991). *An analysis of Thai popular songs by using the features of postmodern aesthetics as cultural indicators*. Unpublished Master degree,
- Kramoltrakul, K. (2003). *The impact of globalization to the enjoyment of ESCR in Thai experience*. Paper presented at the Civil society partnerships for democracy: International civil society forum, Ulaanbaatar, Mongolia.
- Krieken, R. v., Smith, P., Habibis, D., McDonald, K., Haralambos, M., & Martin, H. (2000). *Sociology: Themes and perspectives* (Second ed.). Frenchs Forest
- Kropthong, S. (2004). *Wiwatthanakan pleng lukthung nai sangkhom thai [The evolution of country music in Thai society]*. Bangkok: Panthaki.
- Kropthong, S. (2004). *Wiwatthanakan pleng lukthung nai sangkhom thai [The evolution of country music in Thai society]*. Bangkok: Panthaki.
- Kusalasaya, K. (2003). *Botpleng haeng kwam lang sam palang yot nak pleng [Song from the past and the three best songwriters]*. Bangkok:
- Kusalasaya, K. (2003). *Botpleng haeng kwam lang sam palang yot nak pleng [Song from the past and the three best songwriters]*. Bangkok: Mae Kampong.
- LeCompte, M. D., & Schensul, J. J. (1999a). Analysing & interpretative ethnographic data. In *Ethnographer's toolkit* (Vol. 5). London: Altamira.
- LeCompte, M. D., & Schensul, J. J. (1999b). *Design & conducting ethnographic research* (Vol. 1). London: Altamira.
- Lent, J. A. (1995). *Introduction: Asian popular culture*. Boulder: Westview.
- Leppert, R., & Lipsitz, G. (1990). Everybody's lonesome for somebody: Age, the body and experience in the music of Hank Williams. *Popular Music*, 9(3),
- Limpichai, S. (1993). *Kwa cha pen thurakij tape pleng [Before it become the music industry]*. Bangkok: Graduate School, Faculty of Communication Arts, Chulalongkorn University.
- Limpichai, S. (1993). *Kwa cha pen thurakij tape pleng [Before it become the music industry]*. Bangkok: Graduate School, Faculty of Communication Arts,
- Lockard, C. A. (1995). Hey, we equatorial people: Popular music and contemporary society in malaysia. In *Asian popular culture*. Colorado: Westview Press.
- Lockard, C. A. (2001). *Dance of life: Popular music and politics in Southeast Asia*.
- Loetpipat, K.-a. (2002). *Khit kham tham pleng: Silapa kantaeng nuea pleng thai* London: Macmillan.
- Longhurst, B. (1995). *Popular music and society*. Cambridge: Policy. Loveatsundown. (1999). Retrieved 20 December, 2004.
- Lueck, T. L. (1992). One Voice: The legacy of woman singers in popular music. In K. J. Bindas (Ed.), *America's musical pulse : Popular music in twentiethcentury society* (pp. 221-222). Westport: Praeger.
- Luktungfm.com. (2004). *Prawat lukthung F.M.95 [The history of lukthung F.M.95]*.
- Lundy, K. S. (1992). Woman and country music. In *America's musical pulse*: Macmillan.
- Macmillan. Murray, R. (2002). *How to write a thesis*. Philadelphia: Open University Press.
- Mae Kampong. LeCompte, M. D., & Schensul, J. J. (1999a). Analysing & interpretative ethnographic data. In *Ethnographer's toolkit* (Vol. 5). London:
- Malm, K., & Wallis, R. (1992). *Media policy and music activity*. London: Routledge.
- Manuel, P. (1998). Popular music in india: 1901-86. *Popular music*, 7(2), 157-176.
- Manuel, P. (2002). *World popular music*. Retrieved January 20, 2002, from <http://www.grovemusic.com/shared/viewa/article.html?section=music.43179>
- Master degree, Chulalongkorn University, Bangkok.
- Maykut, P., & Morehouse, R. (1994). *Beginning qualitative research: A philosophic and practical guide*. London: The Falmer.
- McDonald, J. R. (1992). Rock and Roll and the working class. In K. J. Bindas (Ed.),
- McLaurin, M. A. (1992). Proud to Be American: Patriotism in Country Music. In K.
- Meksritthongkam, B. (1991). *The study of Thai country music role for the development of quality of life: An analysis of the lyrical contents of pleng lukthung during 1989 and 1990*. Unpublished Master Degree, Thammasat
- Melbourne: Oxford University.
- Merwe, V. (1989). Origins of the popular style: the antecedents of twentieth-century popular music. *Popular music*, 9(3), 375-380.

- Middleton, R. (2002). *Popular music*. Retrieved April 20, 2002, from Monster-Music. (2004). Rock rakchat (Patriotic rock). Bangkok: RS Promotion.
- Moro, P. (2003). Elite music and nationalism in Southeast Asia: How music becomes classical. *IIAS Newsletter*, 31(Research and report).
- Mukdapan, P. (1989). Rueang rao kiaw kab pleng lukthung' [Stories of Thai country music]. In Samnakan-Kanakamakan-Watanatham-Haeng-Chat (Ed.), *Kueng satawat pleng lukthung thai pak song' [The mid- century of Thai country music, section two]*. Bangkok: Amarin.
- Mulder, N. (1997). *Thai Images: The culture of the public world. Chiangmai: multiculturalism and the demise of nationalism in Australia*. Sydney: Pluto.
- Murerji, C. (1992). Popular culture. In E. F. Borgatta & M. L. Borgetta (Eds.), *Encyclopedia of Sociology* (Vol. 3, pp. 1492-1499). New York:
- Murerji, C. (1992). Popular culture. In E. F. Borgatta & M. L. Borgetta (Eds.),
- Murray, R. (2002). *How to write a thesis*. Philadelphia: Open University Press.
- Mutsaers, L. (1990). Indorock: An early Eurorock style. *Popular music*, 9(3), 307- 320.
- Mutsaers, L. (1990). Indorock: An early Eurorock style. *Popular music*, 9(3), 307-
- Nagi, S. Z. (1992). Nationalism. In E. F. Borgatta & M. L. Borgetta (Eds.), *Encyclopedia of sociology* (Vol. 3, pp. 1333-1342). New York: Macmillan.
- Nagi, S. Z. (1992). Nationalism. In E. F. Borgatta & M. L. Borgetta (Eds.),
- Nak kan mueang ma jak chon chan dai [What class do the politicians come from?]. (2004, June 16). Thairath, p. 1. Nak kan mueang ma jak chon chan dai [What class do the politicians come from?].
- Napayon, Y. (1993). *Yuk pleng pasom bap sankeet sampan khong kromprachasampan 2495 [The period of synthesis music of the Public*
- Negus, K. (1996). *Popular music in theory: An introduction*. Oxford: Blackwell. New York: Berg.
- Nga caravan, kruiyai haeng wongkan pleng puea chiwit [Nga Caravan, the principal teacher of song for life]*. (2003, October). Retrieved 12, 9, from <http://www.music.mahidol.ac.th/journal/october2003/interview.html>
- Norahymn, S. (1994). *Sepia E.P.kiat tut [Hatred of transvesite]*. Bangkok: Roxx Rexcords. NSW: Longman.
- Nutasarin, T. (1991). *Kueng satawat pleng lukthung...suepsan khunkha watanatham thai' [The mid-century of Thai country Music.. to preserve Thai culture]*. In
- Opakun, Y. (2001). *Kao raek khong chiwit, kao ti song khon dontri [The first step was my life and the second was the musician]*. Bangkok: Mingmit.
- Orman, J. (1992). Conclusion: The impact of popular music in society. In K. J. Bindas (Ed.), *America's musical pulse : popular music in twentieth-century society* (pp. 281-287). Westport: Praeger.
- O'Shaughnessy, M., & Stadler, J. (2002). *Media and society: An introduction*. Oxford Univeristy. Palmy Khun Lamyai Mike kwa Pikanet Thongkham [Palmy, Khun Lamyai and Mike got the Music Awards]. (2003, April 28). *Khaosod*, p. 1.
- Paper presented at the Second Australian National Thai Studies Conference, Royal Melbourne Institute of Technology.
- Parkes, C. (2000). *Thailand handbook*. CA: Avalon Travel.
- Paul, O. (1998). Introduction: Aspects of the south Asia/ west crossover. *Popular music*, 7(2), 119-122.
- Pirunsarn, W. (2000). *Communicative meaning in the patriotic songs of the four groups of armies*. Unpublished Master degree, Chulalongkorn University,
- Plasketes, G. M. (1992). The business of pop. In K. J. Bindas (Ed.), *America's musical pulse : Popular music in twentieth-century society* (pp. 149-163).
- Pleng puea chiwit tai laew rue yang [Has 'song for life' died yet?]*. Retrieved July
- Plengprachachon. (2004). *Pleng puea chiwit [Song for life]*. Retrieved November
- Pongpaichit, P., & Baker, C. (1996). *Thailand's boom!* St.Leonards: Allen & Unwin.
- Pongpan, W. (2004). *Sombat pudi [The Proper decorum] (22-27 ed.)*. Bangkok: One World. *Popular music in twentieth-century society*. . . (pp. 213-219). Westport: Praeger.
- Pramot, K. (1973). Pleng lukthung [Country music]. *Sayamrat sabdawichan*, 6, 5.
- Prathamapidok. (1995). *Thama kap kansueksa kong thai [Dharma and education in Thailand]*. Bangkok: Moonlanithi Puttatham.
- Prawat Carabao [The history of Carabao]*. (2003). Retrieved December 10, 2004, from <http://www.carabao.net/biography/carabao.html>
- Premrirat, S. (2002, January- December). Pasathai/ pasathin" [Thai/ local Language]. *Pasa lae wathanatham [language and culture]*, 1, 12.

- Puengkunpra, C. (2000). *Mass media strategies for sales promotion of independent music companies*. Unpublished Master degree, Chulalongkorn University, Bangkok.
- Pusinsit, W. (2002). *Satriniyom: Khabuankan udomkhati haeng satawati yisip [Feminism: the movement and ideology of the 20th century]*. Bangkok: Khopfai.
- Radocy, R. E. (1992). The importance of music to people. In K. J. Bindas (Ed.), *America's musical pulse: Popular music in twentieth-century society* (pp. xixviii). Westport: Praeger.
- Rattikan. (2004). *Chiwa prawat Jit Pumisak [Bibliography of Jit Pumisak]*. Retrieved November 11, 2004, from <http://www.Longdo.com/art/art0022.html>
- Redmond, M. (1999). *Wondering Into Thai culture*. Bangkok: Redmondian Insight
- Relation's band in 1952]*. Bangkok: Parallax View. Retrieved August 27, 2004, from <http://www.opticaldisc-Retrieved August 30, 2004, from http://www.luktungfm.com/history.html>
- Lull, J. (1987). *Popular music and communication*. Newbury Park, Calif: Sage.
- Reynold (Ed.), *National identity and its defenders: Thailand today* (pp. 1-32).
- Reynold, C. J. (2002). Introduction: National identity and its defenders. In C. J.
- Ripley, G. (2001). *Thailand industry analysis: Thailand scene and prospects*.
- Rodnitzky, J. (1992). Popular music as: Politic and protest. In K. J. Bindas (Ed.), *America's musical pulse : Popular music in twentieth-century society* (pp. 3-11). Westport: Praeger.
- Rogers, B., & O'Brien, D. (1992). Rock and roll comes to radio. In A. Moran (Ed.), *Stay tuned: As Australian broadcasting reader* (pp. 80-82). Sydney: Allen & Unwin. Routledge.
- RS-Promotion. (2003). *RS Promotion*. Retrieved August 30, 2004
- Rungfapaisarn, K. (2004, September 9). *Grammy marketing unit: MGA set for big revamp* Sage.
- Samakkan, S. (1980). *Sangkom lae watanatham thai [Thai society and culture]*. Bangkok: Mo Po To.
- Samnak-ngan-kanakamakan-watanatham-haeng-chat (Ed.), *Kueng satawat pleng lukthung thai pak song [The mid- century of Thai country Music,*
- Samnak-ngan-kanakamakan-watanatham-haeng-chat. (1989). *Kueng satawat pleng lukthoong thai [The mid- century of Thai country music]*. Bangkok: Amarin.
- Samnak-ngan-kanakamakan-watanatham-haeng-chat. (1991). *Kueng satawat pleng lukthoong thai phak song [The mid- century of Thai country music, section two]*. Bangkok: Amarin. Sap jo taksin padet amnat [A critique of Prime Ministry Taksin]. (2005). *Thairath*, p. 1.
- Sarajutha, T. (2005). Sap namta andaman [Sweeping tears of the Andaman sea]. Bangkok: Warner Music.
- Satayanurak, S. (2002). *Kwamplianplaeng nai kansang chatthai lae kwampenthai doi Luang Wichitwatakarn" [Changing and building Thai nation and Thainess by Luang Wichitwatakan]*. Bangkok: Matichon.
- Seale (Ed.), *Researching Society and Culture* (pp. 349). London: Sage.
- Seale, C. (1998). Qualitative interviewing. In C. Seale (Ed.), *Researching society and culture* (pp. 349). London: Sage.
- Seale, C., & Kelly, M. (1998). Doing and analysing data. In C. Seale (Ed.), *Researching society and culture* (pp. 349). London: Sage.
- Section two]*. Bangkok: Amarin.
- Sen, K., & Hill, D. T. (2002). *Media, culture, and politics in Indonesia*. Melbourne:
- Set-tho, R. (1989). *Kongsang sankom lae watanatham thai [Social structure and Thai culture]*. Bangkok: Thaiwatanaphanit.
- Shepherd, J. (1991). *Music as social text*. Cambridge: Polity.
- Shuker, R. (2001). *Understanding popular music*. New York: Routledge.
- Silkworm Books.
- Sirinthon, P. (1991). Lukthung kap pleng thai [Thai country music and Thai court music]. In Samnak-ngan-Kanakamakan-Watanatham-Haeng-Chat (Ed.), *Kueng satawat pleng lukthoong thai paksong [The Mid- century of Thai country music, section two]*. Bangkok: Amarin.
- Siriyuvasak, U. (1990). Commercializing the sound of the people: Pleng luktoong and Thai pop music industry. *Popular Music*, 9(1), 61-77.
- Siriyuvasak, U. (1990). Commercializing the sound of the people: Pleng luktoong and Thai pop music industry. *Popular Music*, 9(1), 61-77.
- Siriyuvasak, U. (1998). Thai pop music and cultural negotiation in everyday politics. In K. H. Chen (Ed.), *Trajectories: Inter-Asia cultural studies* (pp. 206-227). London: Routledge.
- Siriyuvasak, U. (1998). Thai pop music and cultural negotiation in everyday politics.
- Siriyuvasak, U., Wisarutphit, W., Waranyoo, W., & Klannurak, M. (1993). *Botbat kong rat ni dan kan suea san muan chon [The role of the government in mass communication]*. Bangkok: Nititham.
- Siriyuvasak, U., Wisarutphit, W., Waranyoo, W., & Klannurak, M. (1993). *Botbat kong rat ni dan kan suea san muan chon [The role of the government in mass communication]*. Bangkok: Nititham.

- Sivaraksa, S. (2002). The crisis of siamese identity. In C. J. Reynold (Ed.), *National identity and its defenders: Thailand today* (pp. 33-48). Chiangmai: Silkworm Books.
- Sivaraksa, S. (2002). The crisis of siamese identity. In C. J. Reynold (Ed.), *National identity and its defenders: Thailand today* (pp. 33-48). Chiangmai: Silkworm Books.
- Sklair, L. (1991). *Sociology of the global system*. New York: Harvester-Wheatsheaf.
- Slater, D. (1998). Analysing cultural objects: content analysis and semiotics. In C.
- Stryker, S. (1992). Identity theory. In E. F. Borgatta & M. L. Borgetta (Eds.),
- Suan Dusit Poll: Dara/ nakrong, thisut haeng pi 2542 [Suan Dusit Poll: Super stars of the year1999]*. (1999). Retrieved September 23, 2004, from www.dusitpoll.dusit.ac.th
- Suan Dusit Poll: Silapin/ dara yotniyom 2546 [The most favorite stars of the year*
- Suek ching kluen... [The battle for frequency...]*. (2004). Retrieved August 30, 2004, from http://content.kapook.com/content/publish/article_11747.html Suek Sa.
- Sufficiency economy*. (2004). Retrieved July 19, 2005, from <http://www.nesdb.go.th/sufficiencyeconomyEcon/main.htm>
- Sunwijai-Kasikonthai-Jamkat. (1997). *Thurakit tapepleng: Kwambanthoeng yuk IMF [The music business: The entertainment of the IMF period]*. Retrieved June 6, 2001, from <http://www.thailandindustry.com/2001janFeb/THAILANDINDUSTRYANALYSIS28.htm>
- Tapkallai, K. (1975). *Pleng klom Jit [Songs to comfort your heart]*. Bangkok: Udom
- Taylor, P. (1985). *Popular music since 1955: A critical guide to the literature*.
- Techapira, K. (1999). *Chao civilise: Kanmueang watanatham thai tai ngao IMF [Civilised people: Thai cultural politics within the shadow of IMF]*. Bangkok:
- Thanakit. (2002). *Prawat nayok ratamontri khong thai [Biographies of Thai prime ministers]*. Bangkok: Pyramid.
- Thanomsap, N. (1989). Kwam penma khong pleng lukthung [The story of Thai country music]. In Samnak-ngan-Kanakamakan-Watanatham-Haeng-Chat (Ed.), *Kueng satawat pleng lukthoong thai [The mid- century of Thai country music]* (pp. 31-33). Bangkok: Amarin.
- Thonawanik, S. (1995). Mahakam dontri lae wipitthasana piset ha ratchakarn pleng thai sakon [The music festival of Thai popular music between five reigns]. Bangkok: Amarin.
- Thonawanik, S. (1995). *Mahakam dontri lae wipitthasana piset ha ratchakarn pleng thai sakon [The music festival of Thai popular music between five reigns]*.
- Tinsulanon, P. (2004). Some spiritual dimentions of Thai people. *The journal of the Royal Institutute of Thailand*, 29, 269-274.
- Tinsulanon, P. (2004). Some spiritual dimentions of Thai people. *The journal of the Royal Institutute of Thailand*, 29, 269-274.
- Tonkiss, F. (1998). Analysing discourse. In C. Seale (Ed.), *Researching society and culture* (pp. 349). London: Sage Publication
- Tonkiss, F. (1998). Analysing discourse. In C. Seale (Ed.), *Researching society and culture* (pp. 349). London: Sage Publication.
- Trakunkrasemsuk, C. *Pleng puea chiwit [Song for Life]*. Bangkok: Top Hit.
- Tudor, D., & Tudor, N. (1979). *Contemporary popular music*. Littleton: Libraries
- Turner, G. (1994). *Making it national : nationalism and Australian popular culture*.
- Ungpakorn, J. G. (2001). *Cleansing democracy of socialism*, The school of oriental and African studies, University of London. University, Bangkok. Unlimited.
- Wacharaporn, P. (1995). Sa-nga Aramphi kru pleng 2000 pleng [Sa-nga Aramphi, The music guru of 2000 songs]. In A. Chan-ngoan (Ed.), *Concert choetchu kru pleng krungti sam [The third concert for the music guru]*. Bangkok:
- Walsh, D. (Ed.). (1998). *Doing ethnography*. London: Sage.
- Wanlayangkoon, W. (2002, March 18-24). Pleng lukthung young mai tai hae [Thai country music have not died yet]. *Matichon Sudsabda*, 22, 72.
- Wanlayangkoon, W. (2002, March 18-24). Pleng lukthung young mai tai hae [Thai country music have not died yet]. *Matichon Sudsabda*, 22, 72.
- Warner, C. R. (1992). The roll and image of African Americans in rock and roll. In K. J. Bindas (Ed.), *America's musical pulse : Popular music in twentiethcentury society* (pp. 195-202). Westport: Praeger.
- Wathana, P. (1992). The rise of Thai pop singers to celebrity status and the roles of mass media involved in reinforcing their celebrity status. Unpublished Master degree, Chulalongkorn University, Bangkok
- Wathana, P. (1992). *The rise of Thai pop singers to celebrity status and the roles of mass media involved in reinforcing their celebrity status*. Unpublished Master degree, Chulalongkorn University, Bangkok.

- Wells, A., & Wah, L. C. (1995). Music culture in Singapore: Record companies, retailers, and performers. In *Asian popular culture* (pp. 29-41). Colorado: Westpor: Greenwood.
- Whitely, S. (2003). *Gender & identity too much too young: Popular music, age and gender (UK only)*. London: Routledge.
- Wimmer, R. D., & Dominick, J. R. (1983). *Mass media research: An introduction*.
- Windschuttle, K. (1989). *The media: A new analysis of the press, television, radio, and advertising in Australia*. Ringwood: Penguin.
- Winichakul, T. (1998). *Siam Mapped: A History of the geo-body of a nation*.
- Winichakul, T. (2001). *We do not forget the 6 October*. Paper presented at the
- Wong, D. (1995). Thai cassettes and their covers: Two case histories. In *Asian popular culture* (pp. 43-59). Colorado: Westview.
- Wongsawang, J. (1981). *The guitar ruam pleng hit pi 24 [Year Book of Thai pop song in 1981]*. Bangkok: Wongsawang.
- Wongsawang, J. (1982). *The guitar ruam pleng hit pi 25 [Year Book of Thai pop song in 1982]*. Bangkok: Wongsawang.
- Wongsawang, J. (1983). *The guitar ruam pleng hit pi 26 [Year Book of Thai pop song in 1983]*. Bangkok: Wongsawang.
- Wongsawang, J. (1984). *The guitar ruam pleng hit pi 27 [Year Book of Thai pop song in 1984]*. Bangkok: Wongsawang.
- Wongsawang, L. (2003, January). I.S.song hits. *A day: world music, a special issue (music)*, 77-81.
- Yoosathaporn, M. (1996). Construction of modern women images through Thai popular songs during 1984-1996. Unpublished Master degree, Chulalongkorn University, Bangkok.
- Yoosathaporn, M. (1996). *Construction of modern women images through Thai popular songs during 1984-1996*. Unpublished Master degree, Chulalongkorn University, Bangkok.
- Zuylen, G. v. (1994). Grammy entertainment still dominates market. Retrieved May 20, 2002, from <http://web1.infotrac.galegroup.com>

Author Information

Yang Xiaoli

Krirk University ,Thailand

Li Jia

College of Music ,Shanxi Normal University, China
